

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH PANELS OF PLASTER REINFORCED WITH FIBREGLASS

Alexandre Wahrhaftig, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil, alixa@ufba.br

Laís Brito, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil, laiscostabritoeng@gmail.com

Ricardo Carvalho, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil, ricardoc@ufba.br

Cibele Menezes, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil, cibeles_menezes@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Plaster is a binder used in diverse applications in civil construction. It is a material with low cost, lightweight, and easy to mould, allowing a good finishing surface and presenting resistance to high temperatures. However, the brittle behaviour and low tenacity limit its use. Aiming to expand the field of application of that material, this work studies the mechanical behaviour of sandwich panels consisting of two faces of plaster reinforced with fibreglass fabrics and a core of extruded polystyrene foam. Using software based on the finite element method, computational models were elaborated simulating the four-point bending test.

KEYWORDS

Plaster; Fiberglass; Modelling; Sandwich panel; Extruded polystyrene; Numerical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The need for more sustainable construction with high productivity, less waste, lower cost, and greater quality control, has driven industrialization in the construction segment in recent years (Li et al., 2020). However, still there is a lack of effective public policies to facilitate the development of sustainable construction materials, affirm Sangmesh et al. (2023). Nowadays, sustainability has been defined as the opportunity of reducing costs and improving product performance (Ibrahim et al., 2023). A mean to contribute to that process is developing an industrialized construction based on process automation, mechanization of operations, modularization, and the use of prefabricated systems, says Avetisyan (2020). This has driven the search for new materials and construction processes, for which composites materials have formed a promising area of research and development.

In this context, gypsum appears as a material with adequate properties to form parts, with or without structural purposes, from the union with other material(s). Considering that it is a binder widely used in the manufacture of semi-industrialized components for civil construction, plaster can be used in the production of blocks, panels, plates, in covering ceilings and walls, in thermoacoustic insulation systems and in decorative elements. Plaster is produced from the calcination of gypsum. In Brazil, the mining method employed allows obtaining a high production rate at low cost (Luz and Lins, 2020). In addition, when compared to other binders, such as lime and cement, gypsum can be considered a material with a lower environmental impact, since its production process requires a lower calcination temperature and, therefore, a lower consumption of energy (Melo, 2008).

Gypsum is an abundant, low-cost material that is resistant to high temperatures and fire. Gypsum mortars can be moulded easily. After hardening, they exhibit a smooth, white appearance, with good surface finish and low specific weight. Furthermore, gypsum pastes have a short setting time, thus allowing high productivity. However, gypsum exhibits a characteristic mechanical behaviour of brittle rupture materials due to its low tenacity (Zanotto and Migliori Jr, 1991). The mechanical characteristics of plaster, associated with its fragile behaviour, restrict its possibilities of use in the civil construction sector, making its application in parts with structural functions particularly difficult.

In order to improve the mechanical performance of gypsum and expand the possibilities of using this material, researchers have been studying the use of natural and/or synthetic fibres as reinforcement of the gypsum matrix. The objective that has been pursued is to improve the deformation regime and increase the tenacity of the material through the addition of fibres. The configuration of the pieces normally used with the participation of plaster is that of sandwich-type plates, where a resistant material occupies the external faces and another of lesser resistance serves as core or filling.

Thus, the present work studies the mechanical properties of sandwich panels consisting of an extruded polystyrene (XPS) core and two faces of gypsum reinforced with different amounts of fiberglass fabric layers. The study of the mechanical properties was restricted to the stretch of linear elastic regime and was carried out through numerical-computational analysis based on the hypothesis of geometric non-linearity.

The computational models were elaborated in order to reproduce the four-point bending tests, simulating a standardized procedure for mechanical tests of the same nature, which allows knowing the loading limits, stresses, strains and vertical displacements of the panels. It should be noted that the option for the computational solution resulted from the scenario imposed by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, which limited access and mobility of people, preventing experiments in a physical laboratory.

COMPUTATIONAL MODELING

Primary material properties

The primary materials defined for the formation of the different plates in the computational modelling are foundry plaster, fiberglass fabric and extruded polystyrene foam (XPS). Estimates of the properties of these materials, such as specific mass, modulus of elasticity and Poisson's coefficient were carried out based on the consulted bibliography.

Gypsum was admitted being in the hardened state. The fiberglass fabric considered was 3 x 1 twill, calibrated, with a grammage of 160 g/m² and a thickness of 0.16 mm. The XPS properties followed the specifications for a thickness of 2.0 cm, defined as being the smallest commercially found dimension. The elastic properties of these materials are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Primary material properties

Type of material	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Density (g/cm ³)	Poisson ratio	Strength in compression (MPa)	Strength in traction (MPa)
Hardened plaster	10.3	1.3	0.2	10.6	6.5
Fiber glass	77.00	2.55	0.20	-	-
Extruded polystyrene	0.043	0.036	0.43	-	-

Elaboration of numerical-computational models

After defining the basic properties of the primary materials, computational modelling was carried out based on the finite element method (FEM) in order to know the mechanical behaviour of the sandwich panels under study. The simulation performed considering the linear elastic behaviour of the materials under the assumption of geometric non-linearity.

Numerical analyses were performed in order to reproduce the four-point flexion tests that are standardized for execution in a physical laboratory. In this sense, the numerical tests have objectives correlated to the physical ones, which are to establish loading limits, calculate stresses and deformations and obtain vertical displacements. It is important to remember that in a four-point bending test, the central part of the piece is subjected exclusively to bending, that is, a region is created in which the only active force is the positive bending moment, which leads to the upper position of the central section to be compressed and the inferior to be tensioned.

In the simulation, the sandwich panels are made up of gypsum faces reinforced with fiberglass fabrics and an XPS core. Three types of panels were idealized, all with the same core, however, with different facing materials, according to Table 2, in accordance with Brito (2021).

Table 2: Face materials of the sandwich panels under study

Panel type	Face material	Thickness (cm)	Fibre volume (cm ³)
1	Plaster with 6 layers of fiberglass fabrics	0.74	7.53
2	Plaster with 8 layers of fiberglass fabrics	0.96	10.04
3	Plaster with 10 layers of fiberglass fabrics	1.17	12.55

The dimensions of the sandwich panels were determined according to the criteria established in ASTM C393 (2020) - Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Sandwich Constructions of the American Society for Testing and Materials. In addition to this regulation, the work of Arruda Filho (2015) was used to define the longitudinal and transversal dimensions of the computational models. Numerical “specimens” were established to have a prismatic-rectangular section of 40 cm in length and 10 cm in width, as indicated in Figure 1. The final thickness of each set is the result of the sum of the thicknesses of the constituent parts, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Width and length of sandwich panels

Figure 2: Thickness of sandwich panels

The models were elaborated by using the commercial software SAP2000 (2018). The panels were discretized into 768 solid elements, all in a square prismatic shape, with six faces, eight nodes and 24 degrees of freedom. Each solid element has been assigned the corresponding properties of its constituent material, whether this is a single type or formed by the union of two materials, according to the data in Table 3. It should be noted that when a material is formed from the union of two others with different properties, as is the case of facing materials, the determination of their properties can be done through micromechanical mathematical models.

Micromechanical models make possible to estimate the effective properties of a composite material using the properties of the materials that constitute it. Among the various existing micromechanical models, the Voigt model is an appropriate model to estimate properties such as specific mass and modulus of elasticity, being used to define the properties of the composite that forms the faces of

sandwich panels, as shown in Table 3. These properties are in line with the recommendations of Brito (2021), Yoshihara and Maruta (2019) and Nemcová et al. (2011). The positioning of the supports and the points of application of the forces were established as recommended in the test method and appear in Figure 4.

Table 3: Properties of the constituent materials of sandwich panels

Panel type	Position	Density (g/cm ³)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Poisson ratio
1	Face	1.0462	11.760	0.20
2	Face	1.0466	11.810	
3	Face	1.0469	11.840	
1 to 3	Core	0.0360	0.0434	0.43

Figure 3: Positioning of loads and supports

Once the maximum force to be applied was established, its value was divided by the number of nodes existing on the upper face of the plate, existing in the transverse direction of the model and in the position predicted in the test method. This condition reproduces with reasonable fidelity the contact point of the mechanical actuator of a press, in addition to avoiding stress concentrations in a specific region of the model due to the singularity with which the forces are attributed.

Figure 3: Scheme of application of forces in the computational model

The simulation of a four-point bending test implies carrying out load increments from zero until a pre-established limit is reached. In the present case, the limit is that of the force that induces the normal stresses that end the stretch of linear deformation of the gypsum matrix, sometimes by compression, sometimes by tension. As shown in Table 1, these stresses are -10.6 MPa and +6.5 MPa, respectively. With this, it was possible to establish relations stress-strain in a different way for those stress limits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The definition of composition and geometric percentage relationships in composites is fundamental for the proper evaluation of the results found. Therefore, it is important to note that panel 3 is 10.71% thicker than panel 2 and 24.71% thicker than panel 1. Panel 2 is 12.64% thicker than panel 1. The fiberglass reinforcement volumes used on the composite faces, place panel 3 as having 25.00% more

reinforcement than panel 2 and 66.67% more than panel 1. In the case of panel 2, it has a fiberglass fabric volume 33.33% greater than that the panel 1.

It is of interest to mention that the results obtained for stresses and displacements were taken in the central section of the computational model. The compressive stress at the top position and the tensile stress at the bottom. The vertical displacements were recorded in the lowest position of the section, having been recorded individually in a spreadsheet considering the value produced by each load increment. From there, they were arranged in the form of graphs, which are presented below.

Force-displacement relationships

The force-displacement relationships for the different sandwich panels, obtained in the numerical test, are shown in Figure 4. The analysis of the graph in Figure 4 reveals that the most favourable force-displacement relationship concerns panel 3, followed by panel 2 and then panel 1. It is important to emphasize that the computational models were loaded with forces starting from zero, which were increasing in intervals of 20 N, until the limits established for the tensile and compressive stresses were reached, each one in turn. Considering the compressive stress as the reference, a force of 2240 N could be applied to panel 1, which was responsible for producing a vertical displacement of -1.751 mm. Maximum forces of 2500 N and 2840 N were applied to panels 2 and 3, which induced displacements of -1.394 mm and -1.178 mm, respectively. It is important to note that after these limits the continuation of the curves are not valid and could be suppressed.

Figure 4: Relationship force-vertical displacement under geometric nonlinearity

Considering the tensile stress as the reference, the maximum forces found were 1100 N for panel 1, 1300 N for panel 2 and 1520 N for panel 3. Therefore, it is possible to verify that the maximum force capable of being supported by the panel 3 was 15.18% greater than that of panel 2 and 26.79% greater than that of panel 1. Sandwich panel 2, in turn, presented a loading capacity 11.61% greater than that of panel 1. It is possible to verify that the different results are associated with the composition and thickness of each panel. When increased, these factors favourably intervene to improve the load capacity and reduce the vertical displacements presented by the different plates. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Results found for the load capacity.

Panel type	Vertical displacement		Load capacity (N)			
	Obtained value (mm)	Variation* (%)	In compression stress	Variation* (%)	In traction stress	Variation* (%)
1	1.7510	--	2240	--	1100	--
2	1.3936	-20.41	2500	11.61	1300	18.18
3	1.1783	-15.45	2840	13.60	1520	16.92

*Variation in relation to the previous value; -- indicates value taken as the reference.

Considering the compressive stress, when the thickness is increased by 27% and 30% there are increases in load capacity of 11.61% and 13.60%. If the increase in thickness is 56.76%, the increase in the load capacity of the panels becomes 26.79%. In traction, the corresponding percentages are 18.18%, 16.92% and 38.18%. It is important to note that the change in the thickness of the panels corresponds to a variation in the volume of reinforcement on the composite faces of approximately 33% and 66%. A similar trend was also noted by Prota et al. (2006), Hegger and Voss (2008), Pino et al. (2017), Escrig et al. (2017) and Lecci et al. (2017).

Stress-strain relationships

The graphs representing the stress-strain relationships for the three panels studied are shown in Figure 5, letters (a) and (b), for traction and compression, respectively. The results found for the three panels prove the linear elastic behaviour for both stresses, even though the computer simulation was conducted under the assumption of geometric non-linearity of large displacements.

Figure 5: Stress-strain relationship in bending. Stress and strain in absolute values.

Vertical displacements

The vertical displacements, in percentage terms, were the following: panel 3, 15.45% smaller than panel 2 and 32.71% smaller than panel 1. Sandwich panel 2, in turn, presented a vertical displacement 20.41% smaller than that of panel 1. It is important to note that panel 3 has 33.34% more fibre reinforcement than panel 2 and 66.67% more than panel 1, and that panel 2 has 33.33% more fiberglass than panel 1. Therefore, an increase in volume of reinforcement of approximately 33% and 67% produce reductions around 15% and 33% in the vertical displacements of the sandwich panels.

Observing the thicknesses in relation to the presented displacements, it is verified that increases of 27% and 29% led to a reduction of 12% and 20% in the displacements. For an increase of 56.76% this reduction is 32.71%. In this sense, panels with greater thicknesses and volumes of reinforcements present greater flexural stiffness, measured by the ratio of force per unit length, which can be perceived by the inclinations of the force-displacement curves of each composition. This aspect is confirmed by Avilés et al. (2008), Davies (2001) and Bahei-El-Din et al. (2016).

Stress-strain relations in bending

To reach the compressive limit stress, the vertical force applied to panel 3 needed to be 15.18% greater than that of panel 2 and 26.79% greater than that of panel 1. And that of panel 2, 11.61% greater than that of panel 1. Thus, it is possible to verify that higher loading capacities correspond to higher yarn densities in fiberglass fabrics that are used as reinforcement of the gypsum matrix. This behavior is in line with that described by Salimian et al. (2016). However, it should be noted that Ali and Grimer (1969) observed, in experiments carried out on physical models, that higher levels of glass fibres in the plaster matrix ended up reducing its resistance to compression. This behaviour is corroborated by Avilés et al. (2008), Davies (2001) and Bahei-El-Din et al. (2016).

When the maximum tensile stress is considered as the reference, it is verified that the force that can be applied to panel 3 is 20% greater than that of panel 2 and 38.18% greater than that of panel 1. That of

panel 2 is 18.18% greater than that of panel 1. The corresponding increase in strength in sandwich panels with glass fiber content was also verified by Ali and Grimer (1969), Singh and Garg (1992) and Iucolano et al. (2019).

CONCLUSIONS

The numerical analysis carried out in this work made it possible to know the mechanical behaviour of sandwich panels in a four-point bending test under the assumption of large displacements. According to the results obtained, it is possible to conclude that the thickness of the facing layers exert a favourable influence on the load capacity and on the reduction of vertical displacements of the panels.

It can therefore be stated that, in both cases of analysed stresses, tension and compression, sandwich panels with greater thicknesses and, consequently, greater amounts of fiberglass reinforcements in the facing materials, present greater vertical load capacities, greater stiffness and smaller displacements.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Ali, M. A., Grimer, F. J. (1969). "Mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced gypsum", *Materials Science Journal*, v. 4, n. 5, pp. 389.
- ASTM C393 (2020). "Standard test method for core shear properties of sandwich constructions by beam flexure". *American Society for Testing and Materials*.
- Arruda Filho, B. A. (2015). "Placas cimentícias reforçadas com tecidos estruturais de sisal", *Master Dissertation in Civil Engineering*, Universidade Federal da Bahia, Salvador.
- Avetisyan, R. T. (2020). "Industrialization of Interior Finishing Works in High-Rise Construction", *IOP Conf, Series: Materials Science and Engineering*.
- Avilés, F., México, A. C., Carlsson, L. A. (2008). "Delamination Behaviour of Composites". *Experimental studies of compression failure of sandwich specimens with face/core debond*, Chap. 12, pg. 344-363, Woodhead Publishing. DOI. 10.1533/9781845694821.3.344.
- Bahei-El- Din, Y., Shazly, M., Salem, S. (2016). "Dynamic Deformation, Damage and Fracture in Composite Materials and Structures", *Impact resistance of sandwich plates*, Woodhead Publishing, ISBN 9780081008706. DOI.10.1016/B978-0-08-100080-9.00016-6.
- Brito, L. C. (2021) "Determinação das propriedades mecânicas de painéis sanduíche de gesso reforçado com tecidos de fibras de vidro através de análises numéricas" (*Determination of the mechanical properties of gypsum sandwich panels reinforced with fiberglass fabrics through numerical analysis*). Master Dissertation 2021, Civil Engineering, Federal University of Bahia, Salvador. (In Portuguese, Abstract in English).
- Davies, J. M. (2001). "Lightweight sandwich construction", *Osney Mead*, Oxford OX2 0EL, Blackwell Science Ltd.
- Escrig, C., Gil, L., Bernat-Maso, E. (2017) "Experimental comparison of reinforced concrete beams strengthened against bending with different types of cementitious-matrix composite materials", *Construction and Building Materials*, 137, 317-329. DOI.10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.01.106.
- Hegger, J., Voss, S. (2008). "Investigations on the bearing behaviour and application potential of textile reinforced concrete", *Engineering Structures*, 30(7):2050-2056. DOI.10.1016/j.engstruct.2008.01.006.

- Ibrahim, M., Alimi, W., Assaggaf, R., Salami, B. A., Oladapo, E. A. (2023). “An overview of factors influencing the properties of concrete incorporating construction and demolition wastes”, *Construction and Building Materials*, 367, 130307. DOI.10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.130307.
- Iucolano, F., Boccarusso, L., Langella, A. (2019). “Hemp as eco-friendly substitute of glass fibres for gypsum reinforcement: Impact and flexural behaviour”, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, v. 175. DOI.10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107073.
- Lecci, V., Focacci, F., Rovero, L., Stipo, G., Stefano, M. (2017). “Intrados strengthening of brick masonry arches with different FRCM composites: Experimental and analytical investigations”, *Composite Structures*, 176, 898-909. DOI.10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.06.023.
- Li, L., Li, Z., Li, X. Zhang, S., Luo, X. (2020). “A new framework of industrialized construction in China: Towards on-site industrialization”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, v. 244. DOI.10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118469.
- Luz, A. B., Lins, F. A. F. (2008) Rochas & Minerais Industriais usos e Especificações, CETEM/MCT, Rio de Janeiro.
- Melo, D. C. P. (2012). “Processo de calcinação da gipsita/resíduo em um forno rotativo contínuo para a produção de gesso beta reciclável”, *Doctorate Thesis in Chemical Engineering*, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, UFPE, Recife.
- Nemcová, H. et al. (2011). “Comparison of methods for dynamic young’s Modulus determination in gypsum materials”, *In: 4th international conference of modelling of mechanical and mechatronic systems*, Faculty of Mechanical engineering, Technical University of Košice.
- Pedreño-Rojas, M. A., Flores-Colen, I., De Brito, J., Rodríguez-Liñan. (2019). “Influence of the heating process on the use of gypsum wastes in plasters: Mechanical, thermal and environmental analysis”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 215, 444-457.
- Pino, V., Nanni, A., Arboleda, D., Roberts-Wollmann, C., Cousins, T. (2017). “Repair of Damaged Prestressed Concrete Girders with FRP and FRCM Composites”, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 21(3). DOI.10.1061/(asce)cc.1943-5614.0000773.
- Prota, A., Marcari, G., Fabbrocino, G., Manfredi, G., Aldea, C. (2006). “Experimental In-Plane Behavior of Tuff Masonry Strengthened with Cementitious Matrix–Grid Composites”, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 10(3):223–233. DOI.10.1061/(asce)1090-0268(2006)10:3(223).
- Salimian, A., Hadizadeh, M., Zeini, M. (2016). “Investigations on the Reinforcement of Mechanical Properties of Gypsum Composites Containing E-glass Woven Fabrics”, *Journal of Textiles and Polymers*, 4(1).
- Sangmesh, B., Patil, N., Jaiswal, K. K., Gowrishankar, T.P., Selvakumar, K. K., Jyothi, M.S., Jyothilakshmi, R., Kumar, S. (2023). “Development of sustainable alternative materials for the construction of green buildings using agricultural residues: A review”, *Construction and Building Materials*, 368, 130457. DOI.10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.130457.
- SAP2000 (2018). “Analysis reference manual. Integrated software for structural analysis and design”. *Computers and Structures*, Inc. Berkeley, California.
- Singh, M., Garg, M. (1992). “Glass fibre reinforced water resistant gypsum based composite”, *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 14(1):23-32.
- Yoshihara, H., Maruta, M. (2019). “Mode I J-integral of extruded polystyrene measured by the four-point single-edge notched bending test”. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 222. DOI.10.1016/j.engfracmech.2019.106716.
- Zanotto, E. D., Migliori Jr., E. R. (1991) “Propriedades mecânicas de materiais cerâmicos: uma introdução”, *Cerâmica*, 247(37).